

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF WEB PLATFORM FOR WIRELESS SENSOR AND ACTUATOR NETWORKS USED IN AGRICULTURAL MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *Over the past decade, the Internet and Information Technologies has evolved very rapidly into a worldwide communications medium. Today humankind is doing almost all daily activities at home or workplaces employing information technologies. In this paper, we propose developing a modern web platform that is useable to interact, data exchange and different digital activities between wireless sensor and actuator networks employed in agricultural sector. This work aimed to design and develop a web platform for monitoring of several agricultural parameters, such as soil moisture level, air temperature, humidity level and other important parameters which are important for plant growing and crop health. The main properties of the developed web platform are its reliability, high security and having opportunities of monitorability and controllability.*

Keywords: *Web platform, WSAN, Spring Boot, Vue JS,*

Introduction

A web platform or application is two-sided interactive software program that is executed on a web server and users of the web platform can be accessed through a web browsers or desktop applications. Web platforms are created in such a manner that the development team that created the user interface receives data from it. For your product and marketing plan, this data offers insight into the use, preferences, and interests of your target market. Additionally, you may utilize this information to improve other customer-facing features of your desktop or mobile applications. Application program interfaces (APIs) in online applications allow users to input a lot of data, which is subsequently forwarded to automation.

Developing a web platform is all about setting goals for the purpose of platform. What need does the platform fulfill? The user interface should be designed with that answer in mind. Information about the consumer will come from the user interface, so developers should design the platform to receive and respond to that information. Web development entails tasks like:

- Making sure the web app offers compatibility with different technologies
- Identifying life cycle and optimization metrics
- Building an intelligent, iterative user interface

Related Works

Many researchers have developed wireless sensor and actuator network based smart monitoring, controlling systems for agricultural services connected with web platforms. Each of them has its specific properties, characteristics and advantages. Authors in this article[1] developed a web platform for a IoT application of an irrigation system. The web platform contains numerous web pages, containing login page, monitoring page, operational control page and etc. The web platform enables the users to monitor and manually control the irrigation process. However, the platform displays only air temperature of the field among the physical parameters. Furthermore, the data about the air temperature is received from the online weather forecast API, which cannot be detected with high-accuracy in real – time. On the other hand, the research paper does not include information regarding the backend side of web platform and the communication technique between the wireless devices of IoT and web platform.

Another work[2] presents IoT based smart solution for crop health monitoring through web portal. The developed devices in the IoT system collect the environmental data and transmit to cloud. All the collected data in the cloud is analyzed. The web portal is implemented to support the farmer monitor the crop profile throughout the life cycle. They claim about current monitoring soil moisture, soil temperature, air humidity and air temperature in real-time, and display NDVI spectral images. Several web services were provided on the web portal, including visualization of historical/real data using graphs, weather monitoring, NDVI mapping and correlation between measured parameters.

Moreover, Kresimir Grgic, Ivan Speh and Ivan Hedi deployed web application for IoT based data monitoring solution[3]. The proposed information system includes a web part which consists of client-server three

tier architecture. It includes graphical user interface, application functions and logic and computer storage. In the graphical user interface, functionality of HTML-based graphical user interface has been extended with custom JavaScript/jQuery functions and various jQuery plugins. Features of application are achieved by employing AJAX for communication with Apache web server. Ajax request sent by the client is received from the application layer through PHP scripts.

Besides that, there are many works [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11] that present integration of web applications into IoT based agricultural, military, medical and other different types systems. That means web technology integration helps to increase the reliability, adaptiveness of IoT based projects and creates various new advantages on them.

Objectives

Our proposed web platform is specifically developed for integration of wireless sensor and actuator network which enables farmers to monitor agricultural parameters in real time.

The main objectives of the proposed web platform will be followings:

Easy to use and setup – as the technology advances day by day, the people experience some difficulties to use modern devices due to their complexities. Our proposed platform will be easy to use or set – up even for the gardeners who are far from the technology.

Adjustable threshold values – in order to achieve fully automation and operating the integrated system even with zero human interaction, web platform enables users to configure the threshold values for each of the wireless nodes.

Remotely monitorable – although the integrated wireless network system is installed in the agricultural fields, users can monitor whole the field and even control the actuators form a distance. This enables modern comfortability and flexibility for the humanity.

High security – since the collected data is important and the configured data for automation must be kept reliable, the web platform will be protected using secure algorithm.

Web Platform Development and Implementation

Development of web platform can be done by many programming languages (PL) and their different frameworks. Currently in trend options for backend development of web platforms are Python PL (Django, Flask), Java (Spring Boot), JavaScript (NodeJS), C# PL (.NET) and others. Frontend part is generally developed using HTML, CSS and JavaScript PL. The top

frameworks for frontend part of web platforms are React JS, Vue JS, Angular and others. Among the above-mentioned options, we choose the Java programming language with Spring Boot framework for backend development because of its powerful security, reliability and high operational speed. Furthermore, we prefer Vue JS framework for frontend development due to its lightweight nature, flexibility and size-efficiency.

a) b)

Figure 1. The directory structure of the frontend (a) and backend (b) parts of project

Vue.js and Spring Boot are popular and powerful web technology frameworks, which use MVVM (Model-View View-Model) design pattern and Model View Controller design pattern, respectively. The frontend part and backend of developed web platform includes very well-organized directory structures, which are shown in Figure 1.

Frontend. “package.json” is the static resource package of a project and “components” is a common component library, which can manage the pages of various sections according to the menu level, each page constitutes a view in the form of a single file component. “router” is mainly responsible for the routing configuration module of page jumping. “App.vue” is the root component, which is used to define the overall structure of single page application and “main.js” is the entry file for the project. Each Vue component (or page) generally consists of three parts, which are template, script and style. App.vue is the main Vue component

which initializes all the other components of the project. "main.js" file mainly introduces the Vue framework root components, routing settings and defines the Vue instance (Figure 2).

Backend. Config and security directories include all the configuration and security files of the project. Project APIs are created all the resource files which are located in web.rest directory. As a database we employed PostgreSQL database which offers more complex data types and allows object inheritance. In order to sort and filter project data for different HTTP requests, we made queries for database in repository files. They are used in service files which prepare everything that the API requests need, in turn.

```

src > JS main.js > load
1 import Vue from 'vue'
2 import App from './App.vue'
3 import * as VueGoogleMaps from 'vue2-google-maps'
4 import router from './routers'
5 import axios from './axios'
6
7 import VueApexCharts from 'vue-apexcharts'
8 Vue.use(VueApexCharts)
9 // eslint-disable-next-line vue/multi-word-component-names
10 Vue.component('apexchart', VueApexCharts)
11 Vue.config.productionTip = false
12
13 Vue.use(VueGoogleMaps, {
14   load: {
15     key: 'AIza5WkCF-5fM1x0w2363yDY9htfyr8Q8D-y',
16   },
17 })
18
19 new Vue({
20   render: h => h(App),
21   router,
22   axios,
23 }).$mount('#app')

```

Figure 2. The key codes of main.js file

The developed login page and account pages are presented in Figure3a and Figure 4, respectively. The active nodes of wireless sensor and actuator network which are registered in the web platform are presented in the map part of account page (Figure 4). The devices are shown only for the users who registered them in platform. Besides that, there are several web pages are created such as, user profile settings, wireless devices page in which platform enables users to manage: removing, registering new devices and control the activeness, and others.

a)

b)

Figure 3. Platform login page (a) and new wireless device registration page (b)

The new device registration page gets position of new device in map and device number from the user. User can just click on the point in map where the device should be installed and the platform automatically created the longitude and longitude values of the point. User can change the selected point position manually, as well (Figure 3b).

The external web pages of platform include general information regarding its capabilities, contacts and others. However, it is required to authorize through login page to access the account pages and monitoring or controlling connected wireless devices in agricultural fields. Users are categorized with different roles according to their access right scopes in order to provide the platform with high level authentication.

Figure 4. Platform account page

Conclusion

In this paper, an adaptive web platform is designed and developed in order to interact with multiple wireless sensor and actuator networks specifically used in agricultural monitoring and control systems. The web platform has the capabilities of monitoring field real-time parameters, controlling the actuators which are integrated in the registered wireless sensor and actuators networks and others. Figure 5 presents the real-time and historical data coming from wireless node 1PW. Platform builds a responsive chart for the users to enable monitorability. The main web frameworks to develop the platform are Spring Boot and Vue JS which are currently in top powerful technologies list due to high security, efficient operational speed and other different advantages.

Figure 5. Monitoring chart for WSN nodes

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